

PEDAGOGICAL CONDITIONS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF LINGUISTIC CULTURAL AND COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE OF FUTURE TRANSLATORS

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Abstract: In this article, the pedagogical conditions for the development of linguistic, cultural and communicative competence of future translators are analyzed and recommendations are developed.

Key words: pedagogue, linguistic, communicative, system, improvement, competence, culture, linguistic culture, pedagogy.

INTRODUCTION

The task of improving the system of teaching the national language and culture of the countries whose language is being studied and preparing them for natural communication by developing the linguistic, cultural and communicative competence of future translators is becoming urgent. In this way, information is provided not only about the history, state structure, and national culture of the country whose language is being studied, but on the other hand, in the process of reading texts in foreign languages, specific words (realia), that is, language units without alternatives, phraseological combinations it will be possible to be able to translate aphorisms, to be taught to use speech culture actively and freely in speech communication.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODS. The issues of developing the linguistic, cultural and communicative competence of future translators have been studied by many scientists of the West, the CIS and our country, and even today this process is systematically implemented. Nationality, Linguistic Adequacy, Linguistic, Cultural and Communicative Issues Sh.Abdullayev, I.Vladimirova, M.Javboriyev, Sh.Isakova, N.Isamukhamedova, G.Salomov, I.Komilov, S.Mirzakulov, I.Gafurov, N.Ormonova .

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION. The development of oral speech of translation students requires starting with simultaneous teaching of the language and culture of the country where the language is being studied. Any translation process is a mutual communication between two languages and two cultures, and a great place is given to the study of intercultural communication along with correct and impartial interpretation of intercultural communication. Also, the linguistic and cultural problems of translator training require studying the place of intercultural communication, the situations of cultural adaptation in

translation, and the foreign language lesson as a crossroad of intercultural meeting.

The concept of "integration", which ensures the integrity of the methodological system and inter-disciplinary relations as a rule of educational development in the teaching methodology, created the principles of integration of individual or activity-related, as well as socio-cultural and discursive linguo-didactic approaches into the translation teaching system. When acquiring such knowledge and skills, it is necessary to master the following general principles of the organization of translator training:

- the principle of an individual approach to the training of translators;
- the principle of an active approach in the preparation of translations;
- the principle of social approach in the training of translators;
- the principle of discursive approach in training translators.

Linguistic-cultural and communicative competence implies phonetic, lexical, phraseological, grammatical (morphological and syntactic), stylistic knowledge from the types of speech activities in foreign language practice and independent levels of the language. This competence includes listening, speaking, reading, writing, phonetic, lexical, phraseological, and grammatical skills in everyday practice through various information related to everyday life and surroundings. The knowledge and skills acquired on the basis of these competencies can be the basis for students of the field to be able to use the English language independently in everyday practical situations and special pedagogical activities.

Students in the field of linguistic, pedagogical, psychological-psycholinguistic and methodical principles of foreign language teaching actively serve to develop their linguistic and cultural competence. These principles are interrelated and serve as programming in achieving the educational and methodological goal.

Emphasis was placed on determining the methods of training future translators, on the extent to which the qualifications of learners can be obtained by means of these methods. As a result, the sequence of methods used in the research and the qualifications acquired by the learners were described in the following order: grammar-translation or classical method; correct, inductive or natural method, oral speech approach or situational language teaching method, audio-lingual or oral speech-based method, silent teaching method, group language learning method, disuggestopidi method [1].

By the level of development of linguistic, cultural and communicative competence, we took into account the ability of students to solve certain problems related to learning foreign words, because they use the acquired knowledge and relevant skills in speech. We have come to the conclusion that there are four levels of linguistic and cultural competence development and they are implemented in two academic years. The contents of the levels we offer are as follows [2]:

a) According to A.N. Shamov, the first level of development of linguistic and cultural competence begins with the collection of empirical knowledge - observations of the functioning of lexical units in different communicative contexts (oral and written) [6]. At this stage, the presentation of the semanticization of the new lexicon was organized. As a result, the students of the field got an initial idea about the sound and graphic image of the lexical unit and served to create connections between the foreign word and its meaning. As a result, students of the field acquired the skills of identifying lexical units in given communicative situations;

b) the second level of the development of linguistic and cultural competence includes the task of forming students' skills in using the studied lexical units, establishing strong connections between the lexical units and their meaning. Speech training of lexicons studied at this stage initially helps to strengthen the primary skills of using words of a certain communicative content. At this stage, the communicative basis of the linguistic exercises proposed by us and used in practice served to consistently illuminate the scope of the studied lexical units, to show their communicative capabilities;

c) the third level of the development of linguistic and cultural competence is related to the acquisition of theoretical knowledge about the lexical system of the studied language, that is, the expansion of students' linguistic understanding, thinking and practical experience. This level aims to form students' skills to determine the form, structure and meaning of words, to make a certain contribution to the creation of verbal and semantic organic connections. As a result, the formal side of the studied language is thoroughly mastered, it helps the development of the foreign philological outlook of the students of the field;

g) the final level of linguistic-cultural competence - the fourth level of improvement includes the development of the ability to use lexical units to solve various communicative tasks, that is, to enable students of the field to effectively use previously acquired or learned language tools and individual speech experience allows. The task of this level of competence is related to the

implementation of tasks defined by the lexicon of a foreign language, it involves the effective use of necessary language knowledge, speech skills and abilities, and is focused on solving various communicative tasks in accordance with the conditions of communication.

It was determined that the following national-spiritual factors are important in the development of linguistic, cultural and communicative competence of future translators:

- making the education of a socially active well-rounded person the main goal, paying attention to the scientific, historical and national nature of the educational process, organizing the pedagogical process based on the ideas of humanism, democracy and equality in relation to educational subjects;

- ensuring the unity of national and universal moral values, wide development of the processes of socialization and individualization of students;

- organizing the educational process on the basis of democratic principles, ensuring that it is organized on the basis of the principles of nationalism, freedom, openness (transparency), freedom, equality;

- organization of pedagogical conditions and educational environment necessary for personal development in the educational process, drawing students' attention to issues of their role in the development of civil society;

- helping students and young people to master the criteria of competitiveness as specialists, achieving national identity awareness, multiculturalism, the active application of the principles of diversity of cultures in life processes. In the research process, ethnocultural materials related to the history of the nation were used. In particular, the use of materials about Uzbek culture and its history served to form and improve students' empirical, visual, emotional and emotional knowledge, skills and qualifications about the source.

As part of the research, it was concluded that the following pedagogical tools are effective in developing linguistic, cultural and communicative competences in future translators:

- provision of the educational process with interactive software tools (video, audio, tables, flip-chats, multimedia) and IT technologies;

- the existence of special popular and scientific sources on the topic and the fact that their use is widespread;

- availability of the opportunity to effectively use national values and national cultural factors (conversations, meetings, museum, cinema, theater);

- the possibility of holding meetings with various foreign guests, in particular, ambassadors of foreign countries, their representatives, during the organization and holding of events;

- in order to form practical experiences in teaching foreign languages - the presence of a contingent of teachers who consider the language as their mother tongue and their extensive involvement in the educational process;

- hayotiy voqealarni shuhrat qozongan insonlar bilan bo'lgan muloqotlar orqali muhokama qilish imkoniyatining yaratilishi. Demak, xorijiy tillarni o'qitishda uzviylik va uzluksizlik tamoyilini joriy etadigan eng birinchi shaxs bu – o'qituvchidir. Binobarin, pedagogik faoliyat nufuzini oshirish, uning samaradorligini ta'minlashning muhim omillaridan biri bu ta'lim jarayonida o'qituvchining pedagogik innovatsion faoliyatini tashkil etishdir [3,4].

CONCLUSION. In the training of future translators, it is important to develop communicative competence in students along with basic competencies. The communicative factor implies teaching to conduct communication. The last goal of teaching foreign languages is to acquire the knowledge, skills and abilities to communicate freely in a foreign language environment. Mastering foreign languages at the level of communication, understanding oral and written speech within the requirements of the curriculum, teaching to acquire knowledge and skills to express one's opinion in a foreign language is the main indicator of a teacher's professional activity.

In the process of developing linguistic and cultural competence, future translators master not only the language system, but also the means of expressing their feelings, inner experiences, and desires. In this way, language serves for socialization and individualization as a means of forming the personal "I" of the student. The student's speech acts as a tool of communication and is realized in integral connection with practical activities.

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